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Sustainable Development Goals and Indian Leather Industry

Hay a Khalid Hashmi and Dr. Vandana Dwivedi

Abstract

United Nations Member States in 2015 adopted 2030 agenda for Sustainable development goals where the aim was to encourage sustained growth and development worldwide with peace and prosperity for people and planet by having a long term vision. There are 17 Sustainable Development goals which are to be managed by global partnership of developed and developing countries. Sustainable manufacturing ensures that the manufactured product are economically produced and the manufacturing process is environment friendly by conserving energy and valuable limited natural resources. The ninth goal of the sustainable development goal is related to industry, innovation and infrastructure. Here, the goal is to 'build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation'. In this paper, an attempt is made to investigate as to how Indian leather industry is abiding by these goals and how sustainable leather manufacturing can aid in increasing export earnings for India. This paper is an outcome of a pilot survey done on one of the clusters of leather industry, that is, organized region of Kanpur cluster.

Keywords: *Leather industry, sustainable development goals, export earnings, sustainable manufacturing, long term growth, environment friendly*

INTRODUCTION

There are 17 goals formulated by United nations to achieve 2030 agenda for sustainable development. Participation is by all developed and developing nations as a global partnership for a common goal of world sustainable development. These goals cover basic human needs in present, while keeping in mind the needs of the future generation.

Over the years, working environment has been moving towards economic growth at all costs and at a very rapid pace. In order to achieve this target, the developing nations are

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risking major natural resources by rapidly increasing industrialisation and modernisation which if not implemented properly shall lay a huge impact on long term sustenance of livelihood. Therefore, this is where the relevance of these important sustainable development goals come to play; as these have been a very profound step towards encouraging conservation and preservation of natural resources which shall continue to be a means of human sustenance.

It is important to note here that, each of these goals are explicitly important and that is the reason why they have been formulated in such a way that they shall be interconnected to each other. The precise agenda of these 17 goals laid by United nations 2030 agenda for sustainable development is to work towards developing cities, businesses and communities to meet their current needs for economic growth and development, without sacrificing the future generations ability to meet their needs in the future. This is the reason why each sustainable development goal has environment conservation as its primary motive.

One of the most important factors for ensuring implementation and success of these sustainable development goals is to create environment consciousness among individuals and to create awareness of importance of these goals as with deliberate conscious awareness these goals shall be implemented worldwide. A means of federal mandate implementation can also facilitate success of these sustainable development goals. Rapid urbanisation and industrialisation can have an inclusive growth results by implementing sustainable development goals alongside. Economic benefits through implementing these goals shall be increasing employment opportunities, reducing poverty, promoting economic growth and improving standard of living of individuals. Apart from economical aspects, looking on sociological aspects it can be highlighted that these goals promote social justice and peace in societies by ensuring fair importance to all ecological entities.

SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS AND MANUFACTURING

The meaning of sustainable manufacturing is to undertake manufacturing activity in such a way that, it ensures to minimize environmental damage while conserving energy and natural resources. This concept has a socio-economic benefit that shall be prosperous of the whole ecological well-being. At present, many manufacturing businesses are laying importance on creating a sustainable manufacturing environment so that businesses may enhance but not at the cost of environment well-being. Earlier, only niche and top rated businesses laid importance on sustainable manufacturing but now, with growing customer consciousness around the globe, all leading businesses are incorporating sustainable manufacturing.

There are a few important aspects that are promoting sustainability, some of these are highlighted below:

Operational efficiency of businesses shall be increased by monitoring wastage and that shall eventually have cost benefit in the long run Enhancing competitive advantage by reaching out to new and a more socially aware customer base.

- ❖ Increasing the prestige of brand and reputation of business as it is manufacturing a product that is not harming/damaging anything
- ❖ A long term business viability and success in the form of increased revenues may be ensured with sustainable manufacturing practices
- ❖ Regulatory operations are well regulated and the ease of doing business may be enhanced
- ❖ Increasing collaborative association with external stakeholders

Elements of Sustainable Manufacturing

- ❖ Manufacturing cost: This is the amount that is used to produce/manufacture the product. This has to be regulated and minimised in order to attain sustainable manufacturing output.
- ❖ Power consumption: This is the amount of energy that is used to produce the product. This has to be efficiently consumed in order to attain mechanised sustained manufacturing process
- ❖ Waste management: This is the process where it is decided as to how the waste has to be disposed, re-used and recycled in order to minimise environmental damage and make the most of the waste generated
- ❖ Operational safety: This is the step where, it is ensured that no entity is harmed in the production process
- ❖ Personnel health: This is the step where, it is monitored as to how the safety of workers shall be ensured in the production process so that no worker is harmed in any way and are safeguarded against any risk

- ❖ Environmental friendliness: This step is extremely crucial for the sustained manufacturing process as in this step is ensured that the process of manufacturing the product is not harming environment in any form.

The above mentioned sustained manufacturing process is a generalised process which can be adopted by most industrial units that are manufacturing any product. Although each step is a simplified and essential route towards sustained manufacturing but still many manufacturing units find it difficult to implement them to achieve sustained manufacturing. Some of the commonly observed challenges faced by most manufacturing units are mentioned below:

- ❖ Lack of performance benchmark and standardization of input units is a major factor affecting sustained manufacturing process
- ❖ The cost of environmental manufacturing is too high for small to medium units to afford in daily manufacturing process
- ❖ Lack of awareness of the importance of sustained manufacturing is another factor responsible for many manufacturing units not engaging in sustained manufacturing

Therefore, there is a need to formulate a streamlined centralised model for sustained manufacturing which should be adaptable by all manufacturing units.

OBJECTIVES

As discussed above, all the problems faced for attaining sustainable manufacturing leads towards the objectives of present study. As this is a small scale pilot survey outcome, so the objectives are structured with the intent to as an outline of one of the clusters of leather industry. The objectives of this study are:

- ❖ To access the viability of sustainable development goals in performing manufacturing practices in Kanpur cluster of leather manufacturing process
- ❖ To access the role of adoption to sustainable development goals in increasing export earnings of the firms in Kanpur cluster of leather industry
- ❖ To access the constraints faced by manufacturers in adapting to sustainable development goals in Kanpur cluster of leather manufacturing process

HYPOTHESIS

H_0^1 : Indian leather industry is not abiding by sustainable development goals objectives

H_1^1 : Indian leather industry is abiding by sustainable development goals objectives

H_0^2 : Sustainable development goals have not aided in increasing export earnings for Indian leather industry

H_1^2 : Sustainable development goals have aided in increasing export earnings for Indian leather industry

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for this paper is based on primary data collection. The mode used for primary data collection was a questionnaire including 5 questions related to the objectives of the study. Data is collected from 15 organised leather industry units in Kanpur region. Interviews were taken from the managerial segment of the manufacturing industry. A specimen of the questionnaire schedule is mentioned beneath.

SPECIMEN OF QUESTIONNAIRE SCHEDULE

PILOT SURVEY

In order to investigate the adoption and implementation of sustainable development goals on the industrial sector of India, there has been a pilot survey done on one of the clusters of Indian leather industry; Kanpur cluster of leather industry. This is a very important cluster of the Indian leather industry as this cluster cater towards the need of saddlery manufacturing that is primarily export oriented. Saddlery manufactured in this region has got a GI (Geographical Indication) . Apart from saddlery manufacturing, this cluster is famous for manufacturing varied leather products; ranging from leather accessories to tanned leather that can be used for further manufacturing. The Kanpur cluster of leather industry is further divided into two broad clusters based on their nature of manufacturing:

- ❖ Organised cluster: This includes the area of Unnao, Kanpur Dehat and Banthar. The industries in these areas have majorly adopted an advanced form of manufacturing where they are showcasing the willingness to adapt environmental norms and compliances. Mainly the size of industries are medium to large scale in terms of operational occupancy
- ❖ Unorganised cluster: This includes the area of Jajmau in Kanpur that is mostly using traditional methods of manufacturing and are hesitant to adopt a modernised and environmental friendly technique of manufacturing. Mainly the size of industries are small to medium scale in terms of operational occupancy

The present pilot survey in order to access the viability of sustainable development goals is conducted on the organised cluster of leather industry. The survey has been done on 15 industrial units belonging to organised cluster. Personal interviews with the managing executive and official representatives revealed that they are showing willingness to adopt sustainable development goals as their purchasers/importers of their produce are keeping a mandate on abiding to environmental norms in the manufacturing process as a compulsion to sale of their products. Certain certifications which primarily aim at environment conservation and sustenance in the manufacturing process have become mandatory by big companies giving order for manufacturing their products in India. One of the commonly used association that is famous in this particular industry has been ‘Leather Working Group’ (LWG) . It is a multi-stakeholder group that aims to develop and maintain environmental compliance and performance capabilities of leather manufacturers. Their goals are the same as the ninth goal of sustainable development goal laid by United nations, that is; promoting sustained industrialisation and foster innovation. This working group involves brands, suppliers, retailers and leading technical experts within the leather industry.

Lately, there have been various seminars and programme organized in all clusters of leather industry in India. While interviewing the pilot survey samples of 15 leather firms in Kanpur cluster, it was computed that out of these 15 firms; only 3 firms of the organised cluster have attained LWG certification. A graphical representation of the same as been illustrated beneath:

LWG engages major brands like ZARA, H & M, ADDIDAS and these brands through this group specify that they will only work with manufacturers having LWG certification. LWG certification has certain ratings that lead to categories of meritorious like Gold, Silver and Bronze.

Therefore, it can be concluded from the pilot survey that associations like LWG can be a great motivating aspect for manufacturers in this cluster to abide by the protocols and norms set by these groups to achieve dual benefit of; adherence to environmental norms and manufacturing a good standard product to qualify as a member of this group and attract popular international brands and buyers. This shall eventually facilitate Kanpur to become a manufacturing hub which shall benefit national export earnings in the long run.

TESTING OF HYPOTHESIS

- H0¹ : Indian leather industry is not abiding by sustainable development goals objectives
- H1¹ : Indian leather industry is abiding by sustainable development goals objectives

Since the size of the study is confined to 15 industrial units only. Therefore, a basic statistical estimation on average is taken to test the hypothesis.

The average of firms making efforts to abide by sustainable development goals are 9 out of 15. Making the true difference being 6 firms which are not willing to abide by SDG's into their manufacturing practice. Therefore, in this way the null hypothesis is rejected and alternate hypothesis is accepted ; based of clear majority of firms showcasing willingness to abide by SDG's.

H_0^1 : Indian leather industry is not abiding by sustainable development goals objectives

H_1^1 : Indian leather industry is abiding by sustainable development goals objectives

Since the size of the study is confined to 15 industrial units only. Therefore, a basic statistical estimation on average is taken to test the hypothesis.

While interviewing firms in the sample size, the outcome for SDG adherence having an impact on export earnings for Indian leather industry was very clearly positive as out of 15 firms; 10 firms left that they attracted more export earnings by following SDGs. Making the true difference being of 5 firms. Therefore, the alternate hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

RESEARCH OUTCOME

·While testing the hypothesis it was interpreted that most manufacturing units working on large scale are showing the willingness to abide by sustainable development goals.

❖ But industry fail in eminence of sustainable development goals as they fail in terms of arranging for additional manufacturing cost to allocate towards waste management for sustained manufacturing process.

Please note: This inference is conceived by the above mentioned pilot survey result on Kanpur cluster of leather industry

The second hypothesis represents the case of a fast developing nation like India, abiding by sustainable development goals can directly aid in increasing export earnings as their adherence shall exhibit a more reliable and viable manufactured product that most developed nations are giving due importance to sustained manufacturing process acknowledge.

Please note: This inference is also conceived by the above mentioned pilot survey which highlighted as to how big brands and companies lay down adherence to sustained manufacturing process as a compulsion for purchasing products that have not harmed environment in any form.

CONCLUSION

Sustainable development goals link environmental, economic and social issues in order to ensure sustainable development for people and the planet. Adopting these goals can lead towards a more productive and prosperous environment. India is a fast developing nation that has an increasing young population that if utilised efficiently, can contribute towards the nation's aim of reaching the status of developed nation. But, an increasing population of the country is a major constrain in the pathway of reaching its development rate. Imparting education to the population is also an important element of Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) as the quality of young population is very important. In order to ensure that this increasing population doesn't become a burden or liability for the nation's growth; a systematic and organised arrangement for skill training to young working population as per their capabilities is essential.

There is a need for federal intervention in all aspects of sustainable development goals and along with the federal support, adequate awareness and education of manpower is essential to reap the benefits of these goals in the long term.

It can be concluded that after evaluating various reports through secondary data and a hands on pilot survey on one of the industrial sector of the nation; it can be stated that if the nation realises the importance of these sustainable development goals, it can work towards the aim of becoming a developed nation. The massive young population needs training and education to become an asset for the nation's growth and create an environment friendly surrounding, which can lead towards nations growth by attracting export earnings, increasing nation's participation on global agendas and operations, creating a manufacturing hub, attracting FDI's.

Therefore, each and every goal of sustainable development goals is extremely important for a nation's inclusive and prosperous growth.

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